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Rural - Urban Mobility: Impact on Farming Productions and Distributions. A Case Study of Osun State Local Government Area, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The frictions encountered in urban- rural movements particularly raw materials and farming produce necessitates provision of motor able roads particularly; industrial society's man lives today. This paper intends to address lopsidedness in mobility infrastructural provisions in Ola Oluwa and Iwo local government area, Osun state, Nigeria. The study analyzed the effects of moving rural produce and distributions to urban areas and the cost-profit's relationships arising from bad transport landscape in recent times, in the study area. The study population consists of 3,500 farmers in ten settlements. Purposive sampling technique and random sampling technique were used, noted for crops farming, random sampling technique was used to select 360 farmers out of the 3,500 farmers from the ten rural settlements in two local governments of Osun state. Primary and secondary data were used; non-parametric research tools were employed for the analysis of data collected. The regression results indicate a strong relationship between transportation variables and delivery efficiency ($R^2 = 0.673$), as well as between transportation cost and farmers' profitability ($R^2 = 0.452$). The study found out that malady in the movements of farmers' inputs and outputs had brewed lots of shortages to the rural farmers' income. It, however, recommended that actionable policies and skillful transport experts should be entrusted with rehabilitation and periodic examinations on the progress of rural road maintenances in the study area.

Keywords: Rural transport, agricultural distributions, rural-urban linkages, transport cost, infrastructure, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Transportation is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of economic development due to its role in facilitating spatial interaction and economic integration (Banister, 2018 and Rodriguez, 2020). In agrarian economics such as Nigeria, rural transportation systems are particularly vital because they enable the movement of agricultural inputs to farms and outputs to markets (Starkey *et al*, 2013 and World Bank, 2019). Efficient transport networks reduce transaction costs, improve market access and enhanced productivity among rural farmers (Minten, et al 2016). Despite these benefits, rural transportation infrastructures in Nigeria remains grossly under- developed. Studies have shown that over 60% of rural roads in sub- Saharan Africa are in poor condition, significantly limiting accessibility (Foster and Briceno-Garmendia, 2010, AFDB, 2020).

According to (Gbadamosi and Olorunfemi, 2016 and Adeniji 2019), in Nigeria specifically, rural roads are often unpaved, poorly maintained and highly susceptible to seasonal disruptions such as flood and erosion. These infrastructural challenges increased travel time, transportation costs, and post-harvest losses, thereby reducing farmers' incomes and overall agricultural productivities (Adewoyin and Akinyosoye, 2020).

Furthermore, the imbalances in infrastructural investment between rural and urban areas as contributed to the widening spatial inequalities, urban centers typically received greater attention in terms of road construction and maintenance, while the rural areas remain neglected (Lipton, 1977, Bates 1981 and Tacoli 2017).

In Osun state, agriculture constitutes a major economic activity, particularly in rural areas such as Ola- Oluwa and Iwo local governments. However, the

inefficiency of rural transport systems in these areas poses significant challenges to the movement of farm produce. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the extent to which transportation infrastructure and costs influence agricultural productions and distributions in the study areas.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigeria's federal government infrastructural expenditures that were budgeted for overall means of transportation do not truly feasible on the rural transport constructions and maintenances of the existing ones which majorly link the rural areas to the urban areas to ease efficient movements that would enhance cost -effective movements of farm produce, desirable incomes for the farmers as rural areas have potentials to feed huge proportions of developments concentrated in urban industrial productivities with their raw materials supplied and other essential materials of living, Olusogo *et al* (2018).

While previous studies have examined farmers' perceptions of transportation policies (Ajitoni *et al*. 2020), there remains a significant gap in empirical research on the relationship between transportation efficiency, delivery reliability, and farmers' income. In particular, limited attention has been given to the cost profit dynamics associated with poor rural transport systems. This study addresses this gap by analyzing the impact of transportation infrastructure and cost on agricultural distributions and farmers' profitability in Osun state.

Hypotheses to Study

H₀₁. There is no effect of road transportation on delivery of farming produce to urban areas.

H₀₂. There is no effect of transportation cost on farmers' profits in the study area.

Conceptual Framework

Development: The meaning of development is conceived as a process involving changes in structures, attitudes and institutions as well as the acceleration of economic advancement, the reduction of inequality and eradication of poverty (Muoghalu, 1992, Salisuet *al*,2014).

Rural Areas: Anele, (2012), submitted that, life in the rural areas is hard, rustic and sometimes inhuman conditions. Many rural dwellers are traumatized by poverty, starvation and diseases. Despite the fact that an overwhelming proportion of our national population reside in the rural areas, the rural areas are characterized by depressingly meager annual per capita income, pervasive and endemic poverty, manifested by widespread hunger, malnutrition, poor health, general lack of access to formal education, livable housing and various forms of social and political isolation compared with their urban counterparts (Muoghalu, 1992,Salisuet *al* 2014).

Rural Development: It is the process of raising the standard of living and financial security of those who reside in rural, frequently remote, and sparsely inhabited places. It, however, involves comprehensive strategies- including infrastructure, education, and economic diversification- to foster sustainable, inclusive growth and reduced poverty, which can be enhanced by quality planning, and pragmatic transportation policy, (Wikipedia, 2025).

Rural Transport: Olurotimi and Akinola (2024), submitted that rural transportation plays crucial role in agricultural production and livelihood of farmers in developing countries. Elements of rural transportation include- railways, roads, waterways, bridges, merchant marine, pipelines as well as Airport and airlines, (Wikipedia, 2025).

Theoretical Review

This research was gravitate towards three theories with a view of their relevance to the existing transportation constrains, currently faced in terms of inefficiency of flows and biasness in terms of provisions of rural transportation infrastructures and been previously adopted in empirical studies used of it as a framework of the analysis in a similar geographical setting within Nigeria, confirms their relevance, (Balogun, 1992, 1995 and 2000).

Theory of Dualism

The theory that is commonly utilized to have a clear understanding of the nature of the development in the space economy of ex-colonial countries such as Nigeria, is dualistic theory. The theory was formulated by a Dutch economist, Boek, as early as 1911, but did not appear in English until 1953. It attempted to combine in one system, a theory for an advanced economy as well as for the backward one. This type of co-existence of two economic systems in a given space economy resulted from the penetration of a capitalist mode of production into the otherwise backward, pre- industrial society. Its main enduring effect is the emergence of spatial differentials in pattern of development (Balogun, 2001). These postulations made it possible to identify the more developed and less developed regions in a space economy.

The approach of geographers to the utilization of this theory as a framework of analysis is spatial. It identified divergent rates of development hence, the resultant inequality in the spatial pattern of economic development in the different settlements and regions of a space economy, (Balogun , 2001).

The Central Place Theory

There are various factors which determine the location of settlements and their

interactions in relation to the nature of activities performed. Chris Teller's (1933) becomes imminent. It is a transportation principle which connects higher-order places that is market areas (Urban centers) and lower-order places, the villages settlements, (Rural areas) pivots to agricultural productions. Chris Teller underpinned the need of inter-dependence among various locations to enhance efficient delivery reliability of raw materials and produce, when elimination of transport frictions is made.

Urban biased Theory

To address market shortcomings and encourage investment in agriculture, government action is required (Binswanger and Deininger, 1997). Policies that prioritize urban productions and urban dwellers only exacerbate agricultural market failures and are major obstacles to long-term prosperity.

He observed instances in sub-Saharan Africa where agricultural policy was strongly prejudiced against rural growth during the post-World War II era. Exportable cash crop producers were compelled to sell their goods at low prices to national marketing boards, which made significant profits on global markets. Due to severe green logistics, rural areas suffered from stunted growth and decreased investments, fewer public goods provision, and political repression.

The degree of urban-rural redistribution, which can be improved by effective green logistics, particular domestic laws and regulations for agricultural markets, trade policies, and the distribution of political rights, must be measured in order to assess the degree of urban bias in any given society. Researchers have resorted to employing data on unequal public goods provision, household consumption levels, overvaluation of the currency rate, and producer support estimates in the lack of

any comprehensive measurements. While advanced industrialized nations strongly promote green logistics, agriculture, and rural residents, urban bias has been proven to be a prevalent phenomena in poor countries, particularly persistent in Africa over time, when employing these imperfect measurements (Anderson and Hayami, 1986).

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Olaoluwa and Iwo local governments, found in the South-Western part of Osun state, Nigeria. The state is situated in the tropical rainforest, which lies between latitude 70° , 30° N⁰ and S Longitude 4° , 30° E and W. It covers about 9,251 km² (357259m). According to the 2006 census, the total population of Osun state is about 3,416,959 and ranked 17th out of 36 states. It has in total thirty (30) local government areas, and area office Modakeke, the primary (third tier) unit of government in Nigeria, (Ajani, 2000). Rainfall figures between 1,500mm and 2,000mm, (Wikipedia, 2007), tree crops, such as cashews, oranges, cocoa, cola nuts, walnuts, palm trees are grown. Root crops like cassava, yam, cereals like maize, guinea corns as well as leguminous plants such as beans, groundnuts, melon and okra and other vegetables are also grown in the areas and a few of these occur in various mixtures. The common arable crops are maize, cassava, yam and cocoyam which are cultivated by about 50 percent of the farming households; the minor crops include pepper, guinea corn, cowpea, melon, beans and cocoyam (Ajani, 2000).

The mean monthly temperature is around 27° C with very little variation in March. The rainy season starts in March and lasts till November; June and July are usually wettest months for the area, (Wikipedia, 2007).

The study population includes about 3,500 farmers in the ten villages' settlements under study two local governments, five settlements under each of them.

Purposive sampling technique for crops producing farmers, simple random sampling techniques were used to select 3,500. The study employed Taro Yaro Yamane to calculate the sample size resulted to 360 farmers.

Primary and secondary sources of data, and structured questionnaires were used to receive relevant data to the findings in the study area for the purpose of research. Secondary sources of data such as journals, articles, internet and published books and past research works were also used to derive needed information for the research.

The questionnaires were forwarded to transportation experts to ensure validation. They were required to judge the correctness of the questionnaires on the effects of transportation on the inter-

dependence of rural- urban, productions and distributions of farming goods particularly, where the researcher might have been unconscious to identify.

The data were collected through the administration of structured questionnaires to the respondents the researcher assisted the farmers to fill the questionnaires as majority of them are semi-literates or non-learned persons.

The analytical tool used for this research is non- parametric statistics specifically, simple regression analysis for hypotheses one and two, using Special Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) for the analysis of the data collected.

Model of Specification

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4 X_4 + e.$$

Where: Y= Dependent variable,

a= constant,

b= coefficient of regression,

x= coefficient of independent variables;

e= error term.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Model Summary of effect of available transportation on delivery of farm goods to urban areas.

Model	R	R. Square	Adjusted R	Std. Error of the Estimate Square
	1.820 ^a	.673	.669	.351

Source: Field survey, (2026).

Table 2: ANOVA of effect of transportation on delivery of farm goods to urban areas.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	90.165	4	22.541	182.737	.000 ^b
Residual	43.791	355			
Total	133.956	359			

Source: Field survey, (2026)

Table 3: Coefficient of effect of transportation on delivery of farm goods to urban areas

Model	Coefficients	Unstandardized		Standardized		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.433	.128	.	3.384	.001
	Transport supports mobility	.906	.065	.845	13.938	.000
	Transport enhance flow of tools	.021	.060	.021	.351	.726
	Transport provides connectivity	-.053	.033	-.068	-1.606	.109
	Transport enhances high cost of movement	.014	.019	.023	.770	.442

Source: Field survey, (2026)

Table 4: Model Summary of effects of transportation cost on profits of the farmers in the study area.

Model	R	R.Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.672 ^a	.452	.445	.364

Source: Field Survey, (2026).

Table 5: ANOVA of transportation cost on profits of the farmers in the study area.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	38.660	4	9.665	73.101	.000 ^b
	Residual	46.937	355	132		
	Total	85.597	359			

Source: Field survey,(2026).

Table 6: Coefficient of transportation cost on profits of the farmers in the study area.

Model	Coefficients	Unstandardized		Standardized		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.005	.182	.511	.000	
	Transport increases cost of goods	.754	0.52	.583	14.408	.000
	Transport is conducive for farmers	-.216	.051	-.273	-4.188	.000
	Transport supports delivery of bulky goods	-.078	.094	-.077	-.828	.408
	Transport provides goods at expected time	.111	.068	.125	1.634	.103

Source: Field survey, (2026).

Discussion of the Results

From Table 1 above, the model shows R the relationships between dependent variable (transport available) and independent variables (transport supports mobility, flow of farm tools, connectivity and cost of movement) account for 82.0% about 18.0% cannot be accounted for. The R^2 which shows the contributions of independent variables on dependent variables accounted for 67.3%, about 32.3% cannot be accounted for which showed that the statistic is a good fit of data

From Table 2 above, the F-ratio is 182.737 and the variables are positively significant at $0.00 < 0.005$ threshold level. It shows that available transport has negative effects on the delivery of farm goods in the study area. This is corroborated by Ukwu (1980), who maintained that, without transport, demand and supply are restricted through the high cost of moving goods, this in turn, affects the living condition of rural people, since development is hampered.

From Table 3 above, the Coefficient of transport supports to the mobility has the highest Beta value of 84.5 % followed by the enhancement of high cost of movement followed by 77.0%. Transport enhancement of flow of tools, connectivity provided for followed of 7.26 and 10.9 are insignificant respectively, while other values are positively significance.

From Table 4 above, dependent variable (cost of movements on other predictors has 67.2 % whereas about 32.8% cannot be accounted for which shows that, the statistical values are a good fit of data. R^2 which shows the contributions of independent variables on dependent variables i.e. cost of movement in the study area.

From Table 5 Above, the F-ratio 73.101 and ANOVA of transportation cost on profits of the rural farmers is significant at $.000 < 0.05$ threshold level i.e. the variables tested were statistically significant. This implies that the hypothesis two which states that there is no effect of transport cost on farmers profit in the study area is rejected while the alternative hypothesis which states that the cost of moving goods have effect on farmers` profits has significant effect thus, statistically significant. That is why Abumere (1993), maintained that much of the farmers` produce could not get to the markets easily, and this consequently dampened their productive efforts, also restricted demand for food crops among the villages, the effect of this spatial restriction created an artificial local glut. This, therefore, depressed prices of agricultural produce, with strong negative impacts on the farm income of the villagers.

From Table 6.0. Above, increase in transport cost affects the profits of the farmers with the highest beta value 58.3%, followed by transport making goods available at expected time 12.5%. All the variables tested were statistically significant except delivery of bulky goods and time of delivery.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study shown that, rural transport inadequate flows of tools have significant effects on available transportation operations in rural areas in Nigeria. Allied to increased cost of movements, convenience during movements of the farmers and movements of bulky produce have accelerated effects on the transport cost and profits of the farmers, in the study areas.

In the study, the findings also showed that the level of interdependency among rural and urban settlements is critical,

particularly, movements of farm produce and farmers themselves for social-economic activities, ins and outs, thus cannot ultimately provide essential support for farmers' productions and industrial goods distribution in rural-urban settlements resultant from bad roads landscape. It is observable that, if the present condition persists, the rural and industrial developments would continue to suffer, and farmers would continue to wallow in abject poverty.

RECOMMENDATION

It, however, recommended that, governments and non-governmental agencies including other organs in the national transport ecosystem should wake into the responsibilities to paddle the rehabilitations and maintenances of rural logistics, and avoid lopsidedness in allocations of transport infrastructures in Nigeria's community as soon as possible, to enable them play the targeted roles.

Transportation organizations should view itself has been in the transportation industry rather than in the narrow areas of urban transportation. Also, heterogeneous markets should be segmented into homogenous units so that all corporate and marketing efforts can be effectively directed to the desired segments.

Beyond those, there should be a sensing or monitoring unit to give feedback on whether the transport experts are attaining its goal or otherwise.

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